

LANGUAGE AND SPEECH CULTURE IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI: ANALYSIS FROM THE ASPECT OF LINGUISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15515403>

Abstract

This article analyzes the issues of language and speech culture in Alisher Navoi's ghazals from the perspective of phonetics (phonology). The article studies phonetic features such as pronunciation of sounds, harmony between sounds, melodiousness and rhythm in Navoi's work, and their role as a means of artistic expression. It also shows the harmony of sounds in ghazals and their influence on speech culture, beauty and aesthetics of the language. The results of the research confirm that Navoi's works are rich and perfect in terms of language culture and phonetics, and bring new perspectives to the fields of Uzbek linguistics and literary studies.

Keywords: *Alisher Navoi, ghazal, language culture, speech culture, phonetics, phonetics, pronunciation, artistic expression.*

Introduction: Language is one of the most important tools of human culture, and its beauty and correct use depend on the level of speech culture and language culture. The work of Alisher Navoi occupies a special place in the development of the Uzbek literary language. Navoi is known not only as a great poet, but also as a scientist who paid great attention to the issues of language and speech culture. His ghazals are a unique source that demonstrates the richness, beauty and melodiousness of the Uzbek literary language.

In ghazals, the phonetic aspects of the language, that is, the system of sounds, their pronunciation, melodiousness and rhythmic properties, as well as the role of sounds in artistic expression, are of particular importance. Phonetics, as a branch of linguistics that studies the system of pronunciation and sounds, allows for a deeper analysis of these processes. In Alisher Navoi's ghazals, the harmony of sounds, their compatibility with each other, the culture of pronunciation and the aesthetic aspects of speech show their uniqueness.

Therefore, in this article, the language and speech culture in Navoi's ghazals are studied from the aspect of phonetics (phonology), and the artistic and cultural functions of sounds are analyzed. This study not only serves to reveal new aspects of Navoi's work, but also offers new approaches to research conducted on the basis of phonetics in linguistics and literary studies.

Main part: Alisher Navoi is one of the greatest figures of Uzbek literature, and his ghazals are considered a high example of the elegance of the language

and the culture of speech. In Navoi's ghazals, special attention is paid to the correct and beautiful use of language, clear expression of meaning, melodiousness and rhythm of speech. This, in turn, served to further develop the culture of language and speech culture.

Phony is a branch of linguistics that studies pronunciation and the sound system, studies the formation of sounds, their interaction, and the culture of pronunciation. The harmony of sounds, melody, and rhythm play an important role in Navoi's ghazals. The pronunciation of each word in the ghazals, the harmony of sounds, and artistic means such as alliteration and assonance enhance the sound culture. For example, alliteration, which is often used in Navoi's ghazals - the repetition of the same sounds - provides the melody and rhythm of speech, which helps the ghazals to be memorable and effective.

In Navoi's work, sounds are not only a means of expressing meaning, but also a means of artistic expression. The melodiousness, intonation, melody and rhythm of sounds enhance the emotional and aesthetic impact of ghazals. From the point of view of intonation, the location and pronunciation of sounds enrich the content of ghazals, increase their musicality. For example, in Navoi's ghazals, certain moods or feelings are emphasized through repeated sounds, which leaves a deep aesthetic impression on the reader.

Today, the study of language and speech culture, including the approach from the aspect of intonation, is an integral part of culture. Navoi's ghazals, as an example of language culture, not only contributed to the development of the Uzbek language, but are also an invaluable source for the study of speech culture.

In modern linguistics and literary studies, Navoi's ghazals are studied on the basis of phonetics, and their role for language culture and speech culture is being further elucidated.

Analysis and Results: This article draws a number of important conclusions from the study of the language and speech culture in Alisher Navoi's ghazals from the perspective of phonetics (phonology). In the process of analysis, the use of sounds as a means of artistic expression in Navoi's work, their pronunciation and harmony were carefully analyzed.

First of all, the melodiousness and rhythm of sounds enhance the emotional and aesthetic impact of ghazals and immerse the reader deeper into the poem. Such means of repetition of sounds as alliteration and assonance, the harmonious arrangement of sounds ensure the musicality of Navoi's ghazals.

This, in turn, indicates a high level of development of language culture and speech culture.

Also, from the point of view of phonetics, the correct pronunciation and arrangement of sounds in ghazals, the harmony between them further enhance the beauty and culture of the language. This, in turn, allows for a deep analysis of Navoi's works, not only from a literary but also from a linguistic perspective.

The results showed that Alisher Navoi's ghazals are an excellent example of language and speech culture, and studying them from the aspect of phonetics further reveals the means of artistic expression of the language. This study not only helps to understand Navoi's work from a new angle, but also creates a basis for research based on phonetics in the fields of linguistics and literary studies.

In general, the results of the analysis confirm the incomparable importance of Navoi's ghazals from the point of view of language culture and speech culture, and reveal the need for a more in-depth study of these examples of creativity.

Conclusion: The article deeply analyzed the artistic and cultural aspects of the language through the study of language and speech culture in Alisher Navoi's ghazals from the aspect of phonetics (phonology). The pronunciation, melodiousness and rhythmic properties of sounds in Navoi's work increase the meaning and aesthetic value of ghazals, and are manifested as a high example of speech culture.

From the point of view of phonetics, it has been established that the use of such artistic means as harmony of sounds, alliteration and assonance is of great importance for the beauty of language culture and the correct formation of speech culture. These processes serve as important factors of linguistic richness and artistic perfection of Alisher Navoi's ghazals.

At the same time, the article emphasizes the importance of research conducted on the basis of phonetics in the field of language and speech culture, and this aspect of Navoi's work creates the basis for the development of new research directions in linguistics and literary studies.

In general, the analysis of language and speech culture in Alisher Navoi's ghazals from the aspect of phonetics has been proven to be of great importance not only from a literary and linguistic point of view, but also as a cultural heritage

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